

UNMS'10

KONGRES UDRUŽENJA NUKLEARNE MEDICINE SRBIJE

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CONGRESS OF SERBIAN NUCLEAR MEDICINE SOCIETY

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GOJAZNOST KAO KONFOUNDING FAKTOR U INTERPRETACIJI MERENJA ERITROCITA OBESITY AS COUNFOUNDING FACTOR IN INTERPRETATION OF RED BLOOD CELL MEASUREMENT

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Polycythaemia vera (PV) is a clonal disorder characterised by excessive proliferation of the erythroid, myeloid and megakaryocyte lineages in the absence of a definable stimulus and to the exclusion of normal haematopoiesis. In all three sets of diagnostic criteria for PV and its differentiation from secondary, apparent and idiopathic erythrocytosis (the Polycythaemia Vera Study Group criteria from 1975, the British Committee for Standards in Haematology criteria from 1996 and the World Health Organisation criteria from 2001) RBC mass determination with isotope dilution remains an important diagnostic test. Obesity is common in our region and, therefore, and it is important to know how that commonly used reference ranges generate inconsistent results when extrapolated to obese patients. The objective of this study was to compare the various weight-normalization and obesity-compensation

methods in a consecutive series of 40 patients with suspected polycythemia who were referred for red cell mass measurements with ^{99m}Tc red cell labeling. Results were classified as normal, elevated or PV and expressed in milliliters per kilogram (mL/kg) by using the actual patient weight and after adiposity adjustments using ideal body weight, body mass index (BMI) and combinations of height-weight, including body surface area. Results were classified as normal, elevated or PCV. We found considerable differences in the classification of patient red cell mass measurements based on the presence or absence of obesity and depending on the method used for weight adjustment. Obese patients have proportionate reduction in blood flow, blood volume and metabolic activity in adipose tissue, and therefore obesity is a common confounding factor in the interpretation of red cell mass measurements.

IAEA DYNAMIC RENAL ANALYSIS SOFTVERSKI PAKET IAEA DYNAMIC RENAL ANALYSIS SOFTWARE PACKAGE

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The aim of this study is to present IAEA dynamic renal analysis software package which was demonstrated during the last ISCORN 2010 meeting held in Mikulov, Czech Republic.

This non-commercial and platform-independent software package, caters to the needs of the Nuclear Medicine community in developing and developed Member States regarding standardization and education, and provides advanced tools for conducting research and exchange patients' data. The latter allows for receiving advice from professionals in the field by overcoming the barrier of commercial software.

When performing renal dynamic studies it is undoubtedly an advantage to be able to extract a numerical, quantitative parameter, both on the input function (split function) and on the output function (transit and drainage).

In this programme, two different methods are used to calculate the contribution of each kidney to the global renal

function, also known as split renal function or differential renal function. This software utilizes the integral method and the Rutland-Patlak method.

Transit refers to the residence time of a molecule within a given space. Whole kidney transit time refers to the time a substance requires to go through the renal arterial blood before it leaves the kidney. Similarly, parenchymal transit is the time that passes before a substance leaves the renal parenchyma. Drainage refers either to the fraction of tracer which has left the kidney after a given time or, conversely, to the fraction of tracer still residing in the kidney. Presently, the best available methods to assess renal drainage are output efficiency (OE) and normalized residual activity (NORA). Both are independent of the individual input function, which is not the case with other empirical parameters such as T-max.